

Towards a repository and reproducible tools for aquatic flow cytometry data

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WORKSHOP REPORT

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Top: Pep Gasol, Ginger Armbrust, Michael Sieracki, Yoav Lehahn, Emily Peacock, Heidi Sosik, Raffaella Casotti, Angelique White, Paul Berube, Charlotte Lee, Michael Lomas. **Bottom:** Hongbin Liu, Nicole Poulton, Zackary Johnson, François Ribalet, Aimee Neeley, Anne Thompson, Amber York

Summary

In the field of aquatic microbial ecology, flow cytometry has become a crucial tool that provides quantitative information for testing theories and models related to biogeochemistry and population dynamics. However, flow cytometry data is not commonly shared, and reused, within the research community and in educational settings. To address the challenges associated with data sharing of flow cytometry datasets, a community workshop was held in March 2023 in Seattle. The workshop brought together a diverse group of flow cytometry data producers, program managers, and computer programmers, including those affiliated with the Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office. The group identified several areas that present challenges to data quality control and compatibility, such as numerous data types and the absence of standard approaches for data processing. The value of a future ocean flow cytometry portal was discussed, along with considerations for balancing capabilities with a wide range of stakeholders. The participants also recognized the importance of a flow cytometry intercalibration effort and expressed a desire to organize and participate in future intercalibration activities and the development of intercalibration standards. Overall, the workshop served as an important community-building effort for this scientific community, as many participants had never met before, and provided a path forward for future collaborative scientific advances through data sharing, data reuse, and common protocols.

1. Workshop Motivation, Goals, and Structure

Phytoplankton fix atmospheric CO₂, generate biomass and oxygen, recycle nutrients, and form the base of the aquatic food web. Understanding how these small members of aquatic ecosystems organize and function requires accurate assessment of microbial population dynamics across a wide range of temporal and spatial scales. Among the technologies used to measure microbial parameters, flow cytometry holds a unique position as it rapidly collects a large amount of information for major groups of phytoplankton, recording the optical properties of light scattering and fluorescence for tens of thousands of single cells within a few minutes. Flow cytometry has become an essential tool in the field of aquatic microbial ecology, providing quantitative information for testing theories and models of the biogeography and population dynamics. Today, flow cytometers are used routinely at long-term sampling sites in the Pacific and Atlantic oceans and are deployed on oceanographic cruises to resolve the phytoplankton distribution from tens of meters to ocean basin scale depending on the sampling strategy and the automation level.

Through a community survey prior to the workshop, we assessed the current status in how the research community shares flow cytometry data. We found that despite the critical role flow cytometry plays in our understanding of aquatic microbial systems, datasets are either not accessible to researchers or fragmented across different platforms because centralized repositories or data/metadata requirements do not currently exist for aquatic flow cytometry data. Furthermore, the available datasets commonly consist solely of cell abundance and do not include the underlying optical properties, which can provide additional information, such as cell size. The lack of a centralized aquatic flow cytometry data repositories makes it difficult for scientists to conduct meta-analysis of past studies, which are critical for addressing complex ecological questions related to global environmental changes, such as the effects of warmer temperatures and lower nutrient supplies in the surface ocean on phytoplankton biomass and productivity. **In this workshop, we examined the concept of a public repository for the rapidly expanding aquatic flow cytometry data. The aim is to improve transparency, reproducibility, and reliability of data products, and facilitate data synthesis efforts by a wide community of users.**

The workshop laid the groundwork for developing a public data repository dedicated to aquatic ecology, leveraging existing flow cytometry data sets while maximizing the impact and accessibility of future data sets. For this first initiative, we limited the scope to datasets that include optical properties (i.e., light scattering and fluorescence) of pico- and nanophytoplankton population from unstained samples collected in the field. Pulling from the international community, we gathered a group of individuals that include flow cytometry experts, data managers and database support designers (see Appendix A). The members shared the common goal of improving access to flow cytometry data for their individual research programs and the global community.

2. Workshop sessions

The workshop included 3 sessions:

1. The first session was aimed at **identifying a set of critical questions the repository needs to address**. To guide the discussion, we sent a survey prior to the workshop to all participants to identify the main problems we want to solve or improvements we want to enable with the repository.
2. The second session aimed at creating a document that determines the **features and goals of the repository**. We defined the required amount of features the repository must contain to be useful for a variety of stakeholders, such as data producers, modelers, statisticians, and students.
3. The third session aimed at determining **the minimum standards required for reporting datasets** required to inform the quality and reliability of the data shared in the repository.

Finally, we created a list of actions to succeed in planning and developing a funded aquatic flow cytometry repository that addresses complex ecological questions.

2.1. Define scientific and technical questions to be addressed with a central data repository.

The prioritization of scientific and technical questions will guide the design of the central data repository. To determine these priorities, two subgroups identified and ranked the most important scientific and technical questions. The outcome of this work is the list of community research priorities.

Scientific Research Questions and Priorities

1. Global Inventory (magnitude and diversity of phytoplankton biomass)
 - Seasonality and Climatology of microbial biogeography, stock assessments
 - Boundaries of Ecological provinces
 - Basin scale differences in community structure (Atlantic vs Pacific)
2. Global Change (slow change)
 - How do abundance, cell size and biomass of plankton populations change with abiotic forcing (e.g., sea surface temperature, mixed layer depth, vertical changes)?
 - How did global phytoplankton abundance, size and biomass change in the last 20 years?
 - How have ecological provinces boundaries changed in the last 20 years?
3. Phenotype/Genotype/Physiology
 - How physiology changes across space and time (carbon / rates / quotas)
 - How does entropy / diversity of optical measurements relate to aquatic ecosystem functioning?
 - Relationships between phenotype and genotype

4. Disturbance (rapid change)
 - How do mesoscale processes shape aquatic microbial community structure?
5. Satellite calibration
 - Biomass partitioning
 - Refine the ratio between carbon (C) biomass and chlorophyll (Chl) biomass (C:Chl is used by satellite algorithm to estimate ocean productivity)
 - Relationships between photosynthesis rates and irradiance (i.e., PE curves)
6. Capacity building / training / education

Technical Priorities

1. Reanalysis and intercalibration
 - Is my data comparable to others?
 - What is the quality of my data?
2. Curation
 - Define levels of tolerance for quality data (i.e., what is acceptable?)
3. Planning
 - Where can I sample a diverse phytoplankton community?
 - Where are the under sampled regions?
 - Sampling strategies based on biological heterogeneity.

Conclusions

The two subgroups agreed on the high importance of addressing scientific questions related to **global environmental changes and global inventory** through sharing and reuse of aquatic flow cytometry data. This research could be achieved by consolidating a subset of raw data from various sources, including the ocean time-series at Martha's Vineyard Coastal Observatory, Bermuda Atlantic, Hawaii Ocean Times Series, and oceanographic cruises from the Atlantic Meridional Transect and Pacific Ocean (SeaFlow) into a single repository. The central data repository could also serve as a resource for **capacity building, training, and education** of stakeholders as well as new and seasoned flow cytometry analysts.

The two subgroups also agreed on the high importance of addressing technical questions on how to intercalibrate flow cytometry data from different sources. This research could be achieved in multiple steps, starting with a small scale intercalibration exercise, where independent research groups analyze identical samples and compare the results. This intercalibration exercise could also serve as a pathway to engaging more researchers in the field and improving data quality and interoperability in future samples.

2.2. Define the features and goals of the central data repository.

During the second breakout session, the features and objectives of the data repository were developed with a focus on the scientific and technical questions identified in the first session.

Two subgroups were tasked with identifying use cases that pertain to global environmental changes and global inventory. The summary of these use cases is presented below.

Use case - What is the trend in the abundance/size and biomass of *Synechococcus* changing over the past 20 years globally?

Hypothesis - Abundance increases and cell size decreases globally over time.

Features Need to demonstrate operability of QC tools, gating, visualization tools.

1. Ability to store and upload raw data (including metadata). Will require tools for naming ontology, with the ability to query your input data for naming issues (Similar to “Mendeley” web importer) – and mapping to a common NERC (NVS) naming structure.
2. Tools for identifying population (aka “gating”) and for comparing methods among data producers. As a minimum, methods should be able to identify *Prochlorococcus*, *Synechococcus*, picoeukaryotes, chlorophyll containing cells.
3. Tools for estimating cell size. Will require calibration files (see [flowPASS](#) methodology) for converting light scatter to biovolume using either ‘Mie Theory’ or empirical relationship. Will need to differentiate live vs preserved samples.
4. Tools for comparing cytograms (e.g., entropy, earth mover distance). Similarity among different cytograms will be used to make recommendations for gating / cell size conversion.
5. Tools for automated curation and tools for manual curation (manually review / annotate quality of data – flag feature after review – possible crowdsourcing or rate users as possible curators). Different QC flags for different features (gating, sizing, carbon conversion)
6. Export data feature (options for export), with a DOI assigned to each dataset and automatically compiled.
7. FCS export feature (harmonized FCS data + population ID / size / carbon quotas + metadata into FCS header)
8. Visualization of aggregate statistics. Define your subset of interest - filter by space (e.g., latitude, longitude, and depth), time, cruise, contributor name, project, instrument, population, size range, or data quality.
9. Identify highly curated data for education, training, and development (e. g. clustering algorithms)

Other relevant use cases

- “Rescue” HOT data (2015-2020) to estimate cell size and phytoplankton biomass.
- Same use case as above for prokaryotic bacteria or experimental data

2.3. Determine the minimum information required for reporting datasets.

There are several reasons why it is crucial to define the minimum information necessary for reporting raw data files: 1) **Reproducibility**: Providing detailed information about the raw data files used in a study is essential for ensuring that other researchers can reproduce the study's results. This information includes details about the data collection process, such as equipment used, data format, and data storage location. 2) **Transparency**: Transparent reporting of raw data files allows other researchers to assess the quality of the data used in a study, which can be important when evaluating the validity of the study's results. 3) **Interoperability**: Standardized reporting of raw data files can improve interoperability between different data sources and facilitate data sharing and reuse across different research projects.

We discussed conventional metadata vocabulary that comprehensively document research data, such as the Ecological Metadata Language ([EML](#)) adopted by the Ecological Society of America. EML file is designed to support the documentation and management of ecological data across different disciplines, projects, and organizations. It provides a standardized way to describe ecological data, which facilitates data sharing, discovery, and reuse. EML files typically contain information about the data creator, data collection methods, variable definitions, and quality control procedures. Below is a recommendation draft of the metadata relevant to raw flow cytometry data.

Required metadata	Optional Metadata
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Latitude• Longitude• Depth• UTC time (ISO8601)• Analyzed Volume• Data Producer• Fixed / Unfixed• Stained / Unstained• Dilution / Concentration• Prefiltration	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Cruise / experiment Name• Cast #• Bottle ID• R2R Cruise name• Instrument (model / serial number)• Optical configuration• Signal recorded (peak height / area / pulse width)• Sample flow rate• Funding source• Publication• Acknowledgements• Population identification• Beads information• Laser wavelengths• Sheath fluid

Other requirements

The adopted metadata format must be compatible with other databases, so users can easily retrieve environmental data associated with flow cytometry data.

3. Proposed next steps

We will seek support from the [NSF Open Science Ecosystem program](#) to create the central data repository. NSF Open Science Ecosystem program will support open science practices and principles across the scientific community. The program will enhance the transparency, reproducibility, and accessibility of scientific research, and to facilitate the sharing and reuse of research data, software, and other products. The program has two tracks: Track 1 supports the development of pilot capabilities or community-building activities that advance a vision for open science; Track 2 supports projects that are designed to take advantage of the existing open science ecosystem and address community needs.

In the coming 6 months, the group will undertake two initiatives to get ready for Track 2 of NSF-OSE program. First, **an intercalibration project** will be carried out to showcase the comparability of data produced by diverse instruments or research teams. Second, a **prototype database** will be developed, comprising a carefully selected subset of oceanographic cruise and long-term time series program data, that showcases meta-analyses.

3.1. Data intercomparison

The goal of the pilot project is to generate and examine new intercalibration cytometer data to (1) increase comparability among diverse datasets to enable large-scale meta-analyses, and (2) to establish marine flow cytometry community standards and optimal practices for improved data intercomparison in the future. Participant laboratories for this first intercomparison will be limited to the members of the flow cytometry working group.

The first step in the intercomparison will be the calibration of scattering intensities across various instruments. To do so, we will be the convert the light scattering measurements to equivalent spherical diameter based on the Mie theory using a bead mixture of known diameters and refractive indices. Equivalent spherical diameter will then be converted to biovolume and carbon quotas using the equation $fg\ C\ cell^{-1} = 0.261 \times Volume^{0.860}$ (Menden-Deuer & Lessard 2000). For the second step, we will compare these predictions with cultures of known carbon quotas. Particulate C was determined for 6 axenic cyanobacteria cultures and 4 eukaryotic phytoplankton cultures during a set of experiments conducted in 2017 (led by Dr. François Ribalet and Dr. Angelicque White).

- May 31st – A sample of each culture, along with beads mixture, will be sent to all participants to be analyzed on their instruments.
- June 30th – Raw files will be shared among groups for intercomparison using a few analytical methods (e.g., optimized Mie theory, flowPASS).
- August 15th – Preliminary results will be distributed to the participants.
- October 22-25th – Group meeting to discuss optimal practices (tentatively scheduled at Bigelow Laboratory).

Note that before sending the samples, a survey will be sent to all participants to identify metadata needed to calibrate light scattering intensities from raw flow cytometry files.

3.2. Prototype development

The goal of the prototype repository is to demonstrate key capabilities and illustrate a few use cases of large-scale meta-analysis the users will be able to conduct. Key capabilities include 1) to **import raw .fcs files and metadata**, 2) calculate **similarity** with known cytograms, 2) to **identify microbial populations** based on optical properties and 3) to **estimate carbon quotas** from light scattering. Our plan is to utilize the web importer for data import. This tool will extract information from the metadata file to determine the structure and header for each .fcs file that needs to be imported. Users will have the opportunity to validate the results before the final import takes place. Following the import process, the system will automatically calculate the similarity between known cytograms based on Earth Mover distance. Semi-supervised clustering algorithms will be used to suggest cluster/gates based on parameters from the most similar known cytograms. Additionally, if the instrument is associated with a light-scatter calibration file, carbon estimates will be computed.

- May 31st – Import Influx and SeaFlow data from the Armbrust lab into the prototype
- July 30th – Import subset AMT + HOT data into the prototype
- September 15th – Demonstrate gating, normalization of optical properties, biovolume and carbon quota estimation using the prototype.
- October 15th – Draft Open-Science Ecosystem proposal Track 2

4. Acknowledgements

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APPENDIX A: PARTICIPANTS

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APPENDIX B: AGENDA

SCHEDULE OUTLINE

Monday

7 am Breakfast

8 am **Scoping Introductions** (30 min each)

- How public data repositories enhance science and education (Charlotte Lee)
- Lesson learned from the medical field (Nicole Poulton)
- Case studies of large environmental FCM datasets (Heidi Sosik & François Ribalet)

10 am Break

10:30 am **Lightning talks** (3 slides, 3 min in total)

- *Data producer*: 1) instrument, 2) data, 3) questions you want to answer with a central data repository
- *Data manager*: 1) database, 2) tools, 3) applications to FCM and scientific motivations

12 pm Lunch

1:30 pm **Overview survey results** (Anne Thompson)

2:30 pm **Breakout #1** GOAL: Define **scientific** and **technical** questions to be addressed with a central data repository.

- Participants write their questions on sticky notes

3:30 pm Break

4 pm **Breakout #1 (continue)**

- Sort the questions in order of priority

5 pm **Breakout #1 reporting**

5:30 pm day 1 ends

6:30 pm Dinner

Tuesday

7 am Breakfast

- 8 am** **Breakout #2 Goal:** Define the **features** and **goals** of the central data repository.
- Participants list the data and tools needed to address questions from Breakout #1
- 10 am** Break
- 10:30 am** **Breakout #2 (continue)**
- Sort list of data and tools in order of priority
- 12 pm** Lunch
- 1:30 pm** **Breakout #2 reporting**
- 3:00 pm** Break
- 3:30 pm** **Breakout #3 Goal:** Determine the **minimum information** required for reporting datasets
- 5 pm** **Breakout #3 reporting**
- 5:30 pm** day 2 ends
- 6:30 pm** Dinner

Wednesday

- 7 am** Breakfast
- 8 am** **Proposal Outline**
- 10 am** Break
- 10:30 am** **Next phases**
- Potential funding sources
 - List of actions
- 12 pm** Lunch
- 1:30 pm** Workshop end